

Comparative Analysis of Automated FAIR Assessment Tools' results

F-UJI, FAIR Enough, and FAIR Checker

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BIH QUEST
Center for Responsible Research

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Time plan

09:00 – 09:10 – Welcoming

09:10 – 09:45 – Intro into FAIRness of biomedical data and automated assessment

09:45 – 10:00 – Break

10:00 – 11:30 – Group work

11:30 – 11:45 – Break

11:45 – 12:30 – Results presentations and discussion

12:30 – 13:00 – Summary and Wrap-up

Today's goals

- Analyze and discuss the results of the FAIR assessments using three different tools
- Identify strengths, weaknesses, and gaps in current FAIRness automated evaluation
- Suggest recommendations on improvement of tools and/or usability

1.

Introduction – Why FAIRness assessment?

Who can benefit from FAIR data assessment?

- **Researchers** – Visibility and Impact, Collaborations and Reproducibility
- **Funders** – Accountability and Transparency, Data Longevity
- **Data Stewards and Data Managers** – Data Quality Monitoring and Compliance Tracking
- **Librarians** – Data Findability and easier Maintenance
- **Policy Makers** – Data Policies Improvements and Benchmarking

Automated FAIR assessment tools

	F-UJI	FAIR Enough	FAIR Checker
Developer	FAIRsFAIR project	Institute of Data Science at Maastricht University	French Institute for Bioinformatics
Metrics adaptation model	FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics	FAIRMetrics	FAIRMetrics
Installation	Needed	Not needed (API)	Not needed (API)
Pricing	Yes	Yes	Yes

2.

Assessment of biomedical data

Sample presentation (data from 2021)

Figure source: Iarkava A, Nachev V, Bobrov E (2024) Workflow for detecting biomedical articles with underlying open and restricted-access datasets. PLoS ONE 19(5): e0302787. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0302787>

Common repositories in Charité Open Data sample (2021)

Source: <https://quest-dashboard.charite.de/#tabFAIR>

Results of validation with automated FAIR assessment tools

Average for 467 data sets

	F-UJI	FAIR Enough	FAIR Checker
FAIR Score (467)	28.98 %	27.52 %	43.28 %
FAIR Score (general-purpose - 187)	50.51 %	46.94 %	70.86 %
FAIR Score (discipline specific - 280)	14.60 %	14.54 %	24.87 %

Overview of results (sample of 467 data sets)

General-purposed repositories

Discipline repositories

Outputs scorings

	Maturity weightening	Overall FAIR score	Individual group scoring (F / A / I / R)	Individual metrics scoring	Individual tests' scoring
F-UJI	yes	in % and in numbers of total	in % and in numbers of total	in % and in numbers of total	between 0 and 2
FAIR Enough (<i>fair-evaluator-maturity-indicators collection</i>)	no	no	no	no	binary
FAIR Checker	yes	no	no	no	Between 0 and 2

FAIR Data Dashboard at Charité

FAIR assessment by F-UJI

30 %

is the average FAIR score of research data objects in all repositories

n = 621

Click on chart to see corresponding metrics

Size of wedges correspond to the weight of the FAIR assessment sections

Source: <https://quest-dashboard.charite.de/#tabFAIR>

Questions?

3.

Your input is needed!

Let's dive into FAIRness

1. Split into 3 groups
2. Go to the breakout-corner
3. Discuss the following questions in your group:
 - **Overview of the results for your Principle**
 - **Which tool did score 'well'?**
 - **Select one metric for further analysis**
 - **What are the gaps in evaluation of this metric? What does support your findings, e.g. in code or tool's documentation?**
4. Summarize your results, insights or recommendations for presentation in Miro (~10 min)

Vielen Dank

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